

Relationships Between Career Development and Counseling Roles for Teachers and Educational Administration

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Abstract

The heuristic framework that was established by Kutsyuruba, Godden, and Walker (2020) investigates the linkages between early career development (ECTs) mentorship for teachers and resources, degrees of influence, contextual variables, and the role of school leaders. It is possible to utilize it to find formal, assisted, and spontaneous paths to mentorship programs that provide

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early career development opportunities for teachers. This framework is beneficial for reviewing and evaluating programs that are now in place or those are expected to be implemented. It also offers school administrators a helpful perspective by highlighting areas in which ECT requirements are satisfied. This heuristic puts the policy environment surrounding mentoring processes into focus by studying the increasingly varied settings in which training takes place and the ever-increasing policy requirements for a manager's position. The policy environment surrounding mentoring processes is significant, and this heuristic brings it into focus. The findings of more recent studies provide support to the idea that school administrators play a significant part in the delivery of mentorship programs; nonetheless, there is still a need for more study into the precise role that management plays in reducing the impacts of various contextual difficulties. This article analyzes the many techniques and structures that might assist school administrators in developing trustworthy and collaborative relationships with starting teachers and counselors. These connections are important for the success of the school. From this point forward, there is a need to investigate the effect of mentorship and supporting structures that are provided to new administrators, and then establish their function as support figures for ECTs in the schools in which they are now employed. Finally, further study has to be done to investigate the impact that mentorship plays in improving the well-being capacity of school administrators. This, in turn, will improve the well-being of the ECTs the administrators deal with and will assist professionals grow and develop.

Keywords: Teaching, Teachers and Career Development, Teachers, Career Development and Counseling, Career Development Roles, Educational Administration and Teachers

Introduction

Although it has been used for quite some time in the subject of educator preparation, mentoring is still thought of as a novel phenomena in the study of educational administration. In the late 1980s and early 1990s, university-based principal preparation programs and policy makers developed mentoring models for prospective principals as a tool to instill novice principals into the profession. This was accomplished by promoting reflective practice, technical expertise, role

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clarification, and increased socialization. During the early phases of research on mentoring, the major emphasis was placed on the development of rookie principals' ability to acquire new abilities. To be more explicit, the question that was raised was about the ways in which an experienced principle (mentor) may help a rookie principal (apprentice) acquire the abilities that are essential to achieve confidence in school administration.

As more and more people join the field of education administration, mentoring has emerged as an essential component of a successful first year for administrators. Mentoring gives novices with an excellent chance to mingle in the rapidly evolving environment of the industry, therefore preparing them for successful leadership and prosperous futures. On the other hand, there has not been a significant amount of investment put in international mentoring procedures. As a consequence of this, many mentoring programs failed to offer sufficient training for mentors and apprentices, failed to define a clear set of objectives and duties, and made use of techniques that were poorly suited for mentor selection and administration. In conclusion, the heuristic was successful in delivering significant insights into the link between resources, influence levels, and contextual elements in mentoring programs for early career development. It is necessary to do further study in order to investigate these facets in a more fruitful manner and to improve the overall efficacy of mentoring programs in order to foster professional growth and development. Over the course of the last two decades, there has been a substantial change in the research that is conducted on directing school administrators and principals. This study investigates not only the positive outcomes and outcomes of mentoring, but also the problems and barriers that persons in this situation encounter. Homer's epic poem, The Odyssey, is widely regarded as the work that laid the groundwork for the practice of mentoring others. Mentoring is an essential component of human growth. It is devoting one's own time, energy, and knowledge to assisting another individual in expanding their horizons and expanding their capabilities. A mentor and a novice form a dual connection as part of the mentoring process. This relationship serves to help the novice as they become more skilled in their job or craft.

Methodology

The conventional definitions of mentoring presume that there is a power imbalance between mentor and mentee in every mentoring relationship. In functionalist conceptions of mentoring, the relationship is often represented in a hierarchical fashion, with the mentor holding the power of the expert position while the apprentice relies on the mentor's expertise. Researchers who study the early years of education often advocate mentorship as a strategy that might help novice administrators with the day-to-day operations of their schools. The mentor will use their experience to advise and support the rookie principle in areas such as planning, budgeting, personnel management, issue resolution, and efficient time management. They will also use their knowledge to help the novice principal manage his time successfully.

The emphasis of relational mentoring is on a mentor and mentee who work together to cultivate a relationship that is advantageous to both parties involved. This stands in contrast to more conventional mentoring methods, which see the mentor as the client's pre-existing source of authority and competence. Because both the mentor and the apprentice learn together via an intensive, long-term, and developing relationship that increases over time due to the ripple effect, Crow (2012) uses the term "critical-constructivist" to describe relational mentoring. To a critical constructivist, learning is the most important aspect of the mentoring relationship, and this aspect includes the "social construction of knowledge," which may be described as "knowledge that is co-constructed through a process of social negotiation." In conclusion, the findings of this study emphasize how important it is to get a grasp of the many definitions and points of view of mentoring in order to effectively direct and assist school administrators and principals. This study provides vital insight into the efficacy of mentoring programs as well as the prospective research routes that may be pursued in the future by studying the difficulties and obstacles that are experienced by mentors and principals. Relational mentoring is an efficient strategy for building leadership abilities since both mentors and apprentices anticipate making progress, acquiring new skills, and undergoing personal growth throughout the course of the relationship. This strategy has been acknowledged as an excellent tool for the development of leadership qualities (Boerema, 2011; Crippen & Wallin, 2008; Hayes, 2019; Dimmock & Walker, 2004; Reyes, 2003; Villani,

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2006). Hayes, 2019 cites Boerema, 2011, Crippen & Wallin (2008), Hayes (2019), Reyes (2003), and Villani (2006). Nevertheless, it is essential to note that during the length of a mentoring relationship, relational mentoring and functionalist mentoring viewpoints will most likely be present in some form in some capacity. This is the case despite the fact that there will likely be some overlap between the two. Principals are provided with help in making the transition to the role of campus leader as well as in strengthening their personal leadership abilities by using both of these vantage points. This aid is provided not just during the transition time but also after the manager has begun working in his new role.

The issue of the responsibilities that principals play in mentoring may be divided into three broad categories: prospective principals and head teachers who are still enrolled in university-based programs; prospective principals and head teachers who are presently serving as deputy principals or teachers; and principals and head teachers at both the novice and senior levels. The database of research contains empirical studies on mentoring that were conducted between the years 1999 and 2019. According to the results of the study, the issue of the responsibilities that principals play in mentoring may be broken down into three primary categories:

- (1) *prospective principals/Head teachers (still at university-based programmers);*
- (2) *prospective principals/Head Teachers (currently Deputy Principals or Teachers);*
- (3) *principals/Head Teachers (novice and senior).*

The studies that have been conducted on mentoring have mostly concentrated on four primary themes: role clarification for both mentors and apprentices; characteristics of effective mentoring relationships; advantages and repercussions of mentoring; and impediments and hurdles to mentoring. Main mentors who are successful have characteristics such as excellent leadership abilities, the ability to communicate well with others, box and risk taking. They provide new principals with three different kinds of assistance: academic support that is centered on the learning of the students, administrative support that assists them in managing their time so that they can focus on learning and teaching, and emotional support all throughout the mentoring relationship.

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In the context of a mentoring relationship, the mentor does not provide guidance to the apprentice but rather poses introspective questions with the goal of assisting the apprentice in gaining insight into their own life and identifying ways to address challenges. Principal counselors are required to have a strong reputation in the field of management, to believe in and be committed to the process of professional development, and to have the ability to collaborate with principal candidates to assist those candidates in focusing their education on the requirements of their students as well as their own personal and professional requirements.

Requirements

Because of the responsibility that comes with holding the position of serving mentor, an aspiring mentor is more productive than a serving mentor in terms of overall productivity. It is recommended that applicants for the job be picked from among managers who are prepared to serve as mentors on a voluntary basis. Such managers provide a greater degree of productivity when compared to mentors who fulfill the function simply because it is needed of them. Principal mentors are responsible for providing new principals with assistance, establishing objectives, locating learning opportunities, giving constructive comments, and encouraging reflection on experiences. The ability to create and sustain connections with customers that are defined by mutual trust, respect, and professionalism is an essential talent for important mentors, since mentoring entails this creating and keeping of relationships. It is important for key mentors to form connections with their clients that allow them to acquire a true knowledge of their clients' ideas and needs, promote honest sharing and reflection on their experiences, and give opportunities for professional growth and training. World-class principals may benefit from mentoring relationships in a variety of ways, including networking within the profession, engaging in in-depth discourse, and getting clarity about their roles. In addition to this, they place an emphasis on developing professional growth and reflection skills, and they are provided with professional support, empathy, problem-solving abilities, and advanced Glacially problem-solving skills.

For leadership development to be successful over the long term, the quality of the mentoring connection is very necessary. The two most important factors that determine whether

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or not a mentoring relationship will be successful are the combination of a mentor and an apprentice, the amount of time spent in the mentoring relationship, and the availability of adequate time for mentoring sessions. It is essential to take a number of factors into consideration when matching clients with mentors. Some of these factors include the client's professional ambitions, the mentor's interpersonal style, and the mentor's educational requirements. It has been noted that "the mentoring process must be developed in a specific setting," which highlights the significance of the surrounding environment. Apprentices reported an enhancement in their professional learning when they paired with counselors in comparable school circumstances, which was consistent with the findings of research carried out by Anderson and Wasonga (2017) and Hayes (2019). According to the findings of recent studies, mentoring relationships are more effective when combined with the appropriate environment.

Both the mentor and the apprentice need to be fully devoted to the process of mentoring in order for it to progress in a natural way over time. There are two primary ways in which mentoring relationships may be established: officially and informally. Opinions among academics on which method is more productive are split. It is essential to place official confidence on the study done by Hayes and Mahfouz (2020).

Therefore, mentoring is an essential ability for important mentors because it enables them to develop and sustain relationships with customers that are distinguished by mutual trust, respect, and professionalism in their dealings with each other. Mentoring relationships may be established on either a formal or informal basis, with academics being of differing perspectives on which model is more fruitful. Mentors may assist new principals in successfully navigating their duties and positively contributing to the overall success of their school by sticking to the mentoring process and cultivating an atmosphere that is supportive. It is not always the case that the personal attributes or features of the mentor or apprentice are taken into consideration while constructing the assignment; nonetheless, mentoring programs sometimes provide linkages to additional mentoring possibilities. This is due to the fact that rookie principals are assigned a mentor within the context of a structured relationship, which may result in anxious sentiments and tension between the mentor and the apprentice. When two people first try to form a mentoring relationship, they often find it challenging to do so successfully.

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When apprentices intentionally seek out a recognized mentor, friend, or colleague with whom they feel a deep connection or whom they trust and respect, informal mentoring relationships tend to grow more naturally and organically. These kinds of relationships are often founded on links between the mentor and the apprentice, such as similarities in their interests and characteristics of their personalities, and they frequently end up producing a favorable dynamic between the two parties involved. The development of leadership abilities is more significantly impacted by non-formal mentoring strategies, such as socialization and internalization, rather than through formally connected organizations. There are, however, some drawbacks to think about, such as the possibility that the chosen mentor does not possess the respect or knowledge necessary for an effective leader, the possibility that the mentor does not meet the needs of the apprentice, and the possibility that the mentoring sessions do not possess the necessary content to support the transition of the new principal to an effective leader. It's possible that the connection between the school leader and the mentee is more about socializing than it is about professional growth. The total amount of time invested in mentoring relationships, and particularly the amount of time allocated to mentoring sessions, are both key components of successful mentoring partnerships. Studies have shown that the efficacy of apprentices as educational leaders increases when mentors and apprentices spend a significant amount of time together, at least once per month, discussing experiences that are analogous to one another. Even in situations in which the mentors and the apprentices did not have the same experiences, this was still exhibited.

Argument

It takes a large amount of time for mentors and apprentices to learn and grow together. They also need a significant amount of time for contact hours so that they may concentrate on building their leadership abilities. In order for mentees to enhance their leadership abilities, it is essential that they engage in face-to-face conversation with their mentors. Increasing the amount of face-to-face time spent in the mentoring relationship may be accomplished with the use of technologies such as video conferencing. According to research, mentoring is an effective way to enhance school culture, cultivate confidence in instructional leadership, and infuse intelligence

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into the teaching profession. It is essential for newly appointed principals to have access to more experienced leaders who can provide support, encouragement, validation, understanding, as well as knowledge, resources, and communication. Principals absolutely need to possess the information, abilities, and mentalities that are necessary for efficient school administration.

Mentoring may bring several advantages to the person serving in that role, such as the ability to exchange ideas, assist another person in the advancement of their profession, review their own practice, and be inspired by the person they are mentoring. The mentors get benefits in the form of continued professional growth, the development of their own school culture, and the establishment of healthy ties with important stakeholders as a result of their involvement in the mentoring relationship.

According to the findings of Schechter and Firuz (2015), 740 mentors said that they regarded the act of mentoring to be rewarding because it gave them the opportunity to exert their influence on rookie principals and aid them in the process of leadership development. In addition, academics have proposed that mentors improve their leadership skills as a consequence of their involvement in the mentoring relationship. Mentoring is an essential component of the selection process for principals, as well as continuous professional development opportunities. When it comes to developing and sustaining productive mentoring relationships, there are, nevertheless, a few constraints that should be taken into consideration. Time restraints, a lack of familiarity with the mentoring role, and inadequate communication abilities are some of the primary problems that need to be addressed.

It is very necessary to have mentoring programs in order to provide assistance to principals and to develop strong leadership qualities. Having said that, they are furthermore obligated to provide help over a lengthy period of time. Mentoring programs, whether they be online, peer-to-peer, or group-based, may help participants build their self-confidence by allowing them to extend their social networks via the formation and maintenance of mentoring connections. Mentoring networks can also assist participants build self-confidence. College preparation programs have the potential to play a significant part in the establishment of formal mentoring programs by fostering

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the growth of ties between principals, hence facilitating the organic formation of mentoring relationships.

The emphasis of study in the future should be on non-traditional forms of mentoring, such as mentoring networks, online mentoring, peer mentoring, and group mentoring. Mentoring models such as mosaic mentoring, collaborative mentoring, and multi-level co-mentoring are a few examples of the many types of mentoring paradigms.

A significant portion of the work has been concentrated on preparing individuals for their first managerial role and acclimating them to the expanded duties that come with being promoted to management. There is a dearth of data and studies on the subject of the advantages that may be gained by mid-career managers by participating in mentoring programs. Managers who are at this level in their careers have a tendency to work alone and do not always make the time to reflect on their own practices or to seek the required guidance from others. In addition, principals who are just starting out in their professions find great satisfaction in working together with others in their industry. Given the present reality of escalating principle burnout and turnover rates, it is of the utmost need to provide a support structure for principals by means of mentorship. The study that is done in the future on mentoring might investigate how principals impact conscious leadership behaviors, with a particular focus on keeping a healthy work-life balance and managing with the stress that is linked with one's employment. The findings of these research may shed light on the nature of mentoring practices that are necessary to successfully cater to the requirements of mentees as well as those of mentors. As a consequence of this, mentoring is a crucial component of the process of recruiting new principals as well as maintaining the principals' own professional growth. Addressing these challenges and incorporating non-traditional mentoring models such as online mentoring, peer mentoring, group mentoring, and mentoring networks can contribute to a more successful and supportive mentoring environment for all involved. The findings of this study indicate the important role that mentoring plays in the development of school leaders and in providing assistance to those who are currently serving in such capacities. Hayes and Mahfouz (2020) provide a synopsis of a variety of viewpoints on the topic of mentorship for aspiring academics. Because it combines the specificity and reliability of direct measures with the in-depth qualitative viewpoint supplied by indirect measurements, a meta-analysis would be the most

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effective approach for performing such a research because it is this method that brings together the two. The influence of mentoring on the leadership performance of school administrators should be the topic of more research in the future. This research should investigate the relationships between attrition and mentoring, personalities with mentors, and other aspects. To develop a mentorship theory that is more consistent, it will be necessary to use a variety of research methodologies. The development of mentorship programs and the evaluation of their efficacy need the use of randomized controlled trials. The implementation process, the responsiveness of mentorship programs, and the influence on education that is impacted by diverse conditions and cultural diversity may all be illuminated by comparative international studies, which can also give insight into these areas. It is also encouraged to do case studies as well as descriptive and longitudinal research in order to better investigate relationship dynamics and processes.

The Review of the Literature

The literature review that is offered here expands on the work that was done by earlier researchers, such as Hobson and Sharp (2005), who did a complete evaluation of the prior work that had been done on mentoring incoming principals in the UK. The research investigates a variety of subjects, including mentoring programs for newly appointed principals, the efficacy of mentoring programs, the benefits that have historically been associated with new principals, and variables that may impact the efficacy of mentoring programs for newly appointed principals. Over the last fifteen years, numerous elements of mentoring for professional development have been the focus of study conducted by scholars looking at various aspects of mentoring for professional development. These themes include a description of the roles that mentors and apprentices are expected to play, the factors that contribute to the success of mentoring relationships, the benefits and repercussions of mentoring, and the challenges associated with mentoring. However, many academics are of the opinion that mentoring programs in order to be successful, they need to take into account a number of different elements, including mentoring pairings, mentoring setting, and time.

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This study contributes to the expanding body of research on mentoring in general by combining all of the research that has been done over the previous 20 years. Mentoring is still one of the most successful techniques to reaching this aim, and this study adds to the growing body of data on mentoring. The United States of America is where the majority of study on mentoring has been conducted; nonetheless, it is vital to improve future research beyond just comprehending the dichotomy and its influence on principals' growth and support. Instead, it is essential to make progress toward developing innovative and effective ways in mentoring as a professional learning tool for principals to use in order to solve the issues that are specific to their context.

Mentoring school leaders via mentoring networks and virtual mentoring are becoming popular trends, but there is still a lot of room for improvement in both of these areas. These two paradigms have the ability to expand the scope of mentoring work by putting light on the many diverse ways that mentoring may serve as a tool for professional learning and development in a variety of settings, including international and international ones. In other words, these two paradigms have the potential to make mentoring work more accessible to a wider range of people.

The purpose of this research was to evaluate whether or not new replacement teachers in a school get mentoring assistance and advice from colleagues (peer mentorship), as well as from administrators, even in an informal capacity. In addition to this, he investigated the part leadership plays in the mentoring process. A quantitative study technique was used, and teachers were given questionnaires consisting of 51 questions to assess their impressions of informal peer counseling support and the leadership styles of their respective administrators.

According to the findings, new replacement teachers at the school were provided with some level of informal coaching and assistance from both their colleagues and the administration. On the other hand, the level of mentoring help offered by coworkers is far more than that offered by school authorities. Mentoring programs and effective school leadership, especially leadership styles that place an emphasis on assisting others, have been shown to have mutually beneficial associations.

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There is no official information regarding the inquiry that was conducted by Michopoulou, Stavropoulos, and Xafakos (2020), and the results of the study showed that the concept of mentorship does not exist in the world that we live in today. The majority of the time, teachers who are informed about this topic will collect materials from the Internet or discuss them with other specialists. In addition, every year hundreds of new school employees occupy the roles of substitute teachers, and this employment scenario has been consistent within the confines of the education system for the previous 10 years. As a direct consequence of this pre-existing circumstance, freshly hired replacement instructors at the school encounter a great deal of difficulty in their jobs.

As a consequence of this, the findings of this study will be valuable since the idea of "mentoring" has not yet been implemented in public schools, which are environments in which each academic year brings a new teacher who has to be well prepared. As a consequence of this, the findings of this study will be useful. Because it gives newly hired substitute instructors access to specialized assistance and support, mentoring is an extremely vital component of the educational system. According to research conducted on the topic, mentorship programs provide a multitude of benefits not only to the recently employed substitute teacher but also to the school as a whole. Research has shown that participation in a mentoring program decreases the likelihood of a teacher leaving their current job. One of the primary advantages of mentoring is the development of professional abilities for teachers, and research also demonstrates that participation in a mentoring program lowers the risk of a teacher leaving their current position. On the other hand, there are many who hold the opinion that there is no connection whatsoever between involvement in mentoring programs and the level of work satisfaction experienced by teachers.

The purpose of the efforts put into peer mentoring is to develop the abilities of all trainers so that they can engage in learning communities with greater ease and success. This may be shown via the use of peer networks, which promote teacher cooperation and mutual support, boost teacher trust, facilitate learning, and improve professional practice. Additionally, the advantages of mentorship have been established by Law (1997), Smith (1999), Lieberman and Miller (2000), and Rhodes and Beneicke (2002).

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The formation of "peer support groups" inside educational institutions not only promotes the members of the group to engage in professional development activities, but also fosters an atmosphere that is amenable to introspection and the acquisition of new knowledge. It wasn't until the 1960s that the concept of peer support groups was pioneered. Since then, these groups have been shown to improve teachers' feelings of self-worth as well as their confidence levels. A new substitute teacher at a school might feel less alone and more welcomed by the other teachers and staff members working in the school unit when they participate in a mentoring program.

Newly appointed substitute teachers quickly get used to the culture of the school, which has already been shaped to some extent by the long-standing social relationships and friendships that have developed among the majority of the teaching staff. These social formations have a deep comprehension of the institution's culture, both in the past and in the present. On the other hand, the new teacher could not be acquainted with the customs of the new school, and because of his hectic schedule, he can have feelings of emotional loneliness and alienation.

The provision of emotional support to educators is often prioritized above the presentation of ideas for more effective pedagogical practices within mentoring programs. It is likely that the new teacher and the prior teachers will have interactions that will be beneficial to both parties, which may play an essential role in the new teacher's capacity to effectively transition to the new school. A new substitute teacher can learn about the culture and functioning of the school by attending group classes organized by the school, exchanging information with other teachers, having informal conversations in the corridors of the school, and meeting with colleagues outside of school. The natural world should not be overlooked, and it is important to get together with colleagues outside of school.

A considerable input from the leadership of the school is necessary for the process of integrating new instructors. When someone enters a school for the first time, the person who fills in as a substitute teacher is the first person who interacts with the principal or head of the school. When it comes to offering help to new substitute teachers, the administrator plays a very crucial role in the school. It is the responsibility of the administrator to ensure that the substitute teacher is accessible to students in order to answer any questions or concerns that may emerge.

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One of the factors that contributes to individuals leaving the teaching profession is the perception that they would not get enough assistance from administration. One of the reasons why teachers quit their positions is because they are unhappy with the leadership they get in their schools, which demonstrates how important it is for school administrators to fulfill the role that they are assigned. To guarantee that new students get the right amount of assistance and direction, educational districts should make it a top priority to collaborate with school officials.

According to the coalition of excellence (2010), qualified principals who are aware of the criteria for developing support programs and the standards for executing support programs are able to encourage suitable mentoring assistance for new students. This helps ensure that new students have a successful transition into the school. According to Wood (2005), it is the responsibility of the principle to establish the culture of the school, to take the lead in providing mentoring assistance, and to coordinate the mentoring process. When the principal arranges events to create professional connections between new teachers and veteran teachers, Michopoulou, Stavropoulos, and Xafakos (2020) found that new teachers had a greater chance of succeeding in their classrooms.

In addition, Wood (2005) discovered that when teachers have the perception that their professional accomplishments are valued, they have enhanced levels of both self-confidence and comfort. Therefore, it is of the utmost importance that the actions that are done by the leadership of the school be characterized as favorable not only for the newly hired teacher, but also for other members of the school community who are a part of the school community. Behaviours of supportive leadership, working beyond the formal function of the school principal by offering aid to teachers; as a constructor; criticism; suggestions of approved instructors; protection of public interests; treating teachers equally; praising the teachers; being readily understood by teachers; and me) are all examples of these behaviors.

The principle is responsible for a significant portion of the implementation of mentorship assistance programs for new businesses. It is extremely vital for the principle to encourage collaboration among members of the school in order to cultivate an atmosphere that is receptive to creative thought for the newly hired substitute teacher. It is of the utmost importance that the principle participates actively in the mentoring process and carries out their duties in an efficient

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manner. Johnson (2001) gives further statistics demonstrating the need of cooperation between administrators, educators with little to no experience, and seasoned professionals in the field of education. It makes the case that it is the job of the principle to take into account a broad range of criteria and to steer clear of circumstances that might put the participant in danger. In addition, it says that the administration should avoid soliciting extracurricular activities that he or she needs and avoid sending inexperienced new replacement teachers to the school's most challenging kids. Both of these things should be avoided at all costs.

According to Hope (1999), a benevolent leadership style should depict the manager as a nice person rather than a strict authority figure. This is in contrast to the autocratic leadership style. This involves maintaining links amongst colleagues in order to avoid the newly hired substitute teacher from getting the sense that they are separated from the rest of the team and in order to create possibilities for general professional growth. In addition, supportive leadership behavior may involve the act of establishing connections amongst colleagues when this is not the case. This is done so as to avoid giving the appearance that the new substitute teacher is isolated from the rest of the team.

Watkins (2005) suggests using these three tactics in order to effectively demonstrate supportive leadership behavior. Michopoulou, Stavropoulos, and Xenakis (2020) propose the establishment of a mentorship program in which the duty of the mentor is to perform the responsibilities of a developing trainer in order to inspire and motivate newcomers. The second tactic is to make an effort to persuade the manager to take on the responsibility of coordinating and monitoring the operations that are newly implemented. The manager creates an atmosphere that is hospitable to newcomers and paves the path for the diffusion of fresh viewpoints across the company as a result of their actions.

Conclusion

As a result, one effective approach of giving the new teacher with the proper aid in pedagogical problems is to foster talks about academic difficulties between new and old school

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members in line with the idea. This is an important step in the process. Establishing regular meeting hours and offering client feedback that is both relevant and thorough are two tactics that have been proved to be useful for mentoring, according to Roberson (2009), who suggests employing these strategies. The principal is the most significant component of these measures; thus, the principle is the one who should deliver this feedback and urge other staff trainers to do the same. The Greek educational system is extremely centralized, with the central authority being in charge of supervising each and every individual school unit. As a result, there are less possibilities for pupils to take part in extracurricular activities, and new replacement instructors do not have the same level of discretion over their classrooms. As a consequence of this, the principle plays an essential part in the process of giving mentoring assistance to the new replacement teacher and establishing trust between the principal and the new teacher.

According to the findings of the study conducted by Glaraki (2014) and the comments made by the lecturers who participated in the research, the connection between the newly hired replacement teacher and the principal is one that is characterized by collaboration and harmony. When a new substitute teacher takes over a classroom for the first time, it is the responsibility of the principal to ensure that the new teacher is aware of the laws, objectives, and duties of the school from the very first day that they are in charge of the classroom. It is crucial to maintain open communication with the other members of the school and to provide a cordial welcome to the new substitute teacher who will be working there.

New replacement teachers may find it easier to cope with the day-to-day challenges that arise within the school unit if supportive leadership is shown. However, a lack of supporting leadership behavior may add to emotional exhaustion in a teacher and make them less effective in their job. According to studies, the levels of emotional tiredness experienced by newly relocated teachers are significantly reduced in schools that have a culture of collaboration and togetherness among all school educators, as well as a pleasant working environment, cooperation, and support.

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